

I am sorry if my paper eventually lacks in technicalities, I am but an undergrad student and as such I have -with all probability- approached the problem in a very naive way: of course I did my research, grasping the basic concepts behind this beautiful branch of Computer Science, yet I will most likely lack the elegance, diligence and wisdom that an experienced professor might have. That being said, I hope the ideas and the demonstrations (if proved to be logically impeccable), in their novel approach, might share a light on this undoubtedly important problem: not just for academics, but our society in general.

Notice: this paper is a preprint. Pretty much everything inside it needs refinement and editing from someone with more experience than me. If you see an error or margin of improvement I beg you to notify me at the following email address: lorenzo.taborchia@edu.unifi.it
Every kind of constructive feedback is welcomed.

Contents

1	Introduction: what is a 3-SAT problem?	3
2	Resolution is a specific application of the Union Rule	4
3	3-SAT has union width $k=3$	5
4	The Algorithm	7

P = NP: A Polynomial-Time Solution to 3-SAT

Lorenzo Taborchia*

March 17, 2026

1 Introduction: what is a 3-SAT problem?

The **3-SAT** problem is a subcategory of **SAT** (or Boolean Satisfiability Problem): a well-rooted computational theory problem where the computer is asked to find a series of assignments capable of solving a given Boolean formula in *conjunctive normal form* (CNF) ¹. An example of said problem might be²:

$$(x_1 + x_2 + x_4) \cdot (x_3 + x_4 + x_6)$$

This problem has been classified as NP-complete by Cook-Levin's Theorem: that means that 3-SAT is a special problem which solution may be verified in polynomial time and is NP-hard. Hence, each NP problem may be reduced to a 3-SAT since it is within the most difficult NP problems. That is, being able to find such an algorithm that would solve 3-SAT in polynomial time would mean that each NP-problem may be solved in polynomial time. The main challenge in finding a polynomial solution for an NP-hard problem such as 3-SAT is that it suffers from combinatorial explosion: that is brute-forcing³ a 3-SAT instance with n variable would force our machine to check 2^n possible solutions in the worst case scenario. The exponential nature of 3-SAT runs even deeper since classic algorithms such as 'Branch & Bound' or 'DPLL' are not able to solve such a problem in polynomial-time for every instance. This hints to the fact that either 3-SAT has exponential complexity for every possible algorithm made to solve it ($P \neq NP$), or we have to analyze the problem's nature deeper in order to find a polynomial solution ($P = NP$).

*To anyone who exists or has ever existed in my life, however lost.

¹Where the formula consists of a conjunction (AND) of several OR clauses

²From now on I will use the same notation used by Boole in his books: that is, plus sign for ORs and the multiplication dot for ANDs

³Hence checking whether each possible solution solves the problem

2 Resolution is a specific application of the Union Rule

As the reader may know DP's algorithm uses a logical inference rule called Resolution Rule. It states that:

Given A,B CNF clauses and literal x, you have that:

$$\frac{(A + x), (B + \neg x)}{(A + B)}$$

One may also know the Union Rule, it states that:

Given A,B CNF clauses and literals x,y, you have that:

$$\frac{(\neg A \rightarrow x), (\neg B \rightarrow y)}{(\neg A \neg B) \rightarrow (xy)}$$

Knowing that an implication may also be written in clause form as $(\neg Hyp) + Th$, where *Hyp* is the hypothesis (e.g. $\neg A$) and *Th* the thesis (e.g. x), then you may also write the Resolution Rule as:

$$\frac{(\neg A \rightarrow x), (\neg B \rightarrow \neg x)}{(\neg A \neg B) \rightarrow x \neg x}$$

If you notice this means that $\neg A \neg B$ always leads to a contradiction $(x \cdot \neg x)$, hence that:

$$\text{say } A = (a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n), B = (b_1 + b_2 + \dots + b_n),$$

$$C = \{ \text{Given literal } Th \in A \text{ or } B : \wedge_i \neg c_i | c_i \neq Th \}$$

Then given $(\neg A \rightarrow x), (\neg B \rightarrow \neg x)$ you have that:

$$C \rightarrow Th, \forall Th \in A \text{ or } B$$

Example 2.0.1 Say you have 2-SAT clauses $(a + b) \cdot (\neg a + c)$, then :

$$(\neg b) \rightarrow a \wedge (\neg c) \rightarrow \neg a$$

Then:

$$(\neg c \neg b) \rightarrow (a \neg a)$$

So:

$$\neg c \rightarrow b \wedge \neg b \rightarrow c \equiv (c + b)$$

What we are simply doing is writing each resolution clause as a series of implications. Given a CNF 3-SAT clause for example, you have that:

$$(a + b + c) \equiv \neg a \neg b \rightarrow c \equiv \neg a \neg c \rightarrow b \equiv \neg b \neg c \rightarrow a$$

And this may be done with every solvent generated by the Resolution Rule (the mechanism is always the same): we are basically saying that Resolution is specific application of the union rule that end up generating non relevant information (we will prove this in the next paragraph). The fact that Resolution turns out to be an application of the Union Rule is quite useful because it means that:

Theorem 2.0.1 (*Union Rule generates a correct an complete inference system*)
Union Rule generates a correct an complete inference system

Demostration 2.0.1 (*Union Rule generates a correct an complete inference system*)

This is simply due to the fact that:

1. *Correctness: is implied by Union Rule correctness*
2. *Completeness: if Resolution is a subset of Union, and Resolution is complete, then Union is complete*

3 3-SAT has union width k=3

As I said in the previous section each 3-SAT CNF clause may be seen as a collection of three implications:

$$(a + b + c) \equiv (\neg a \neg b \rightarrow c) \cdot (\neg a \neg c \rightarrow b) \cdot (\neg b \neg c \rightarrow a)$$

We may prove by using DP itself that:

Lemma 3.0.1 (*3-SAT has union width k leq 3*)

Every clause of width k derivable from a 3-SAT clause set is equivalent to a set of implications within the graph of pairs, because each 3-SAT resolution step involves at most two premises to produce a conclusion

Demostration 3.0.1 (*3-SAT has union width k leq 3*)

As we know each k-width clause is a product of a series of resolution steps using DP (e.g. derivable): that is, there exists a resolution tree whose leaves are the original input clauses (with width ≤ 3).

1. *Base Case: in 3-SAT, every input clause is already mapped into the graph as a set of pairwise implications (as seen above) and cannot be decomposed without information loss: e.g if you have $ab \rightarrow c$ decomposing it into $a \rightarrow c$ and $b \rightarrow c$ will make you lose relevant info about the problem (you would have decomposed $\neg a + \neg b + c$ into $(\neg a + c) \cdot (\neg b + c)$). The only exception to the rule is if you have $G_1 = G_2$, thus you might have $ab \rightarrow c$ and $ab \rightarrow \neg c$ and end up with $a \rightarrow \neg b$ and $b \rightarrow \neg a$: that is the 2-SAT case, which we know has resolution length $k \leq 2$, that we may still recreate in the graph of pairs as $aa \rightarrow cc \cdot bb \rightarrow cc$. Hence in each base case you get union width ≤ 3 .*

2. *Inductive hypothesis: If R resolvent, then $\exists G_1, G_2$ 'parent' clauses that clash on a single atomic literal x . Say you have R with width $k + 1$; Because of the Inductive hypothesis you may decompose it into its two parents without any information loss: say G_1, G_2 have $\lfloor k/2 \rfloor$ width, yet it does not matter anyway, if you iterate this process (decomposition) you end up with a base case with union width ≤ 2 .*

Example 3.0.1 *Say you have the $A = (a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n)$, then you have that:*

$$(\neg a_1 \cdot \neg a_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \neg a_{n-1}) \rightarrow a_n$$

Say it comes from:

$$(a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_3 + x), (a_3 + a_4 + \dots + a_n + \neg x)$$

They must be resolvents and may as well be decomposed into their parents G_1, G_2 until you get the respective input clauses or 2-SAT clauses.

A direct consequence of this lemma is that:

Theorem 3.0.1 *(Pairwise saturation is sufficient to solve 3-SAT)*

Pairwise saturation is sufficient to solve 3-SAT

Demostration 3.0.2 *(Pairwise saturation is sufficient to solve 3-SAT)*

As stated by Lemma 3.1 we have that given $A = (a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n) \equiv (\neg a_1 \cdot \neg a_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \neg a_{n-1}) \rightarrow a_n$, we may decompose it into its parents, say $G_1 = (a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_3 + x) \equiv (\neg a_1 \cdot \neg a_2 \cdot \neg a_3) \rightarrow x$ and $G_2 = (a_3 + a_4 + \dots + a_n + \neg x) \equiv (\neg a_3 \cdot \neg a_4 \cdot \dots \cdot \neg a_n) \rightarrow \neg x$, and we may repeat this process until we get to the original 3-SAT clauses involved in the resolvents creation. This means that $(\neg a_1 \cdot \neg a_2 \cdot \dots \cdot \neg a_{n-1}) \rightarrow a_n$ does not add any relevant information that was not already encoded in the 3-SAT pairwise implication (e.g $ab \rightarrow c$).

This theorem on its own should suffice in order to demonstrate that 3-SAT is solvable in polynomial time. That is because the problem's complexity has been shown to be linked to its resolution width [3]. With resolution being a specific subset of rules given by the union rule we may as well remove the inefficiencies that resolution carries by upper-bounding the union rule into a 'pairwise' version of it: that is, you apply the union rule to the input if and only if what you end up with has $k \leq 3$. So

Example 3.0.2 *Say you have:*

$$ab \rightarrow c \cdot ad \rightarrow \neg c$$

You may apply the rule since what you end up with is:

$$abd \rightarrow c \neg c \equiv \text{false}$$

Hence:

$$ab \rightarrow \neg d, ad \rightarrow \neg b, bd \rightarrow \neg a$$

Each with width $k = 3, \leq 3$. But if you have:

$$ab \rightarrow c \cdot de \rightarrow \neg c$$

You would end up with:

$$abcd \rightarrow \text{false}$$

Irrelevant to our graph of pairs, since its information is already codified within $G_1 = ab \rightarrow c$ and $G_2 = de \rightarrow \neg c$.

4 The Algorithm

If the only relevant way to use the Union Rule is that shown above then an algorithm that wants to demonstrate if a given CNF 3-SAT formula is satisfiable simply has to map out every edge you may derive from the input, using the Pairwise Union Rule.

```

Input CNF 3-SAT formula
Map out initial edges linked to clause (e.g  $ab \rightarrow b$ )
while New Union Rules can be applied do
    Find new edges by applying every Union Rule possible (that maintains
    width  $\leq 3$ )
end while
if contradictory SCC exist then
    UNSAT
else
    SAT
end if

```

Now, in order to understand how the algorithm determines if a formula in SAT we need to describe what a contradictory SCC is in this context:

Definition 4.0.1 (*Contradictory SCC*)

In a 3-SAT a contradictory SCC is a Strongly Connected Component that contains the following cycle:

$$ab \rightsquigarrow \neg ab \rightsquigarrow a\neg b \rightsquigarrow \neg a\neg b$$

This is due to the fact that the cycle above implies that the (a, b) is completely saturated: that is, each truth value you may give to the (a, b) couple, it will be ruled out by the input. The unit contradiction 2-SAT is known for $(x \rightsquigarrow \neg x)$ will be depicted as a Contradictory SCC where $a = b$, that is:

$$aa \rightsquigarrow \neg a\neg a$$

Now, you may see how the complexity of our algorithm strictly depends on the operations it uses to create the necessary edges, let us call the cost of these operations OP . Then in the worst case scenario our algorithm has to create $O(V^2)$ edges, hence:

$$O((2n^2)^2 \cdot OP) \approx O(n^4 \cdot OP)$$

If you take the code I have published with this preprint you will notice that:

$$OP \approx O(n^4 \cdot n^2) = O(n^6)$$

That is because $COST(nx.descendants) \approx O(V+E) = O(n^4)$, $Cost(litslist\ double\ loop) = O((2n)^2) \approx O(n^2)$. So you end up with:

$$O(n^4 \cdot n^6) = O(n^{10})$$

That is a lot, but still polynomial in time. Due to the completeness of the inference system we have used the algorithm should both be correct and complete. And due to its polynomial nature we should be able to say that $P = NP$. Yet this implication is already implied by Lemma 3.0.1 and Theorem 3.0.1

References

- [1] S.A Cook. The complexity of theorem-proving procedures. *ACM symposium on Theory of computing (STOC)*, 1971.
- [2] Goerdt A. Hirsch E.A. et al. Dantsin, E. A survey of algorithms for the satisfiability problem. *Theoretical Computer Science*, 2002.
- [3] Eli Ben-Sasson e Avi Wigderson. Short proofs are narrow — resolution complexity. *Journal of the ACM.*, 2001.
- [4] Johnson D. S. Garey, M.R. *Computers and Intractability: A Guide to the Theory of NP-Completeness*. W.H. Freeman and Company, 1979.
- [5] Richard M. Karp. Reducibility among combinatorial problems. *Complexity of Computer Computations*, 1972.
- [6] L.A Levin. Universal search problems. *Problems of Information Trasmision*, 1973.
- [7] Pudlák P. Saks M. Zane.F Paturi, R. An improved exponential-time algorithm for k-sat. *JACM*, 2005.
- [8] U. Schöning. A probabilistic algorithm for k-sat and costraint satisfaction problems. *FOCS*, 1999.
- [9] M. Sipser. *Introduction to the Theory of Computation*. Cengage Learning, 2012.